

As soon as panicles began to emerge, the plants were covered with cloth screens to provide 22-26% of full sunlight for 28 d. Check plants were grown in full daylight. The experiment was in a randomized complete block

with six replications.

Grain yield in all varieties decreased significantly with low light exposure (see table). Hashikalmi was least affected, followed by BR9 and Kataktara. BR9 had the highest yields at

both light intensities, and was the least affected modern variety. The highest yield reduction was in BR6, followed by BRI. Filled spikelets were more affected than 1,000-grain weight. □

Effect of low light intensity at ripening on yield and 2 yield components of aus varieties.^aBRRI, Bangladesh.

Variety	Grain yield			Filled spikelets			1000-grain weight		
	Normal light (g/pot)	Low light (g/pot)	Reduction (%) due to low light	Normal light (%)	Low light (%)	Reduction (%) due to low light	Normal light (g)	Low light (g)	Reduction (%) due to low light
BR1	10.98 g	3.96 ef	64 e	73 cd	47 d	36 cd	19.89 e	16.50 g	17 cd
BR3	25.24 b	10.74 b	57 de	81 abc	52 cd	35 cd	25.64 ab	21.91 ab	15 bc
BR6	14.73 f	3.47 f	76 f	85 ab	48 d	44 de	23.82 c	20.03 de	19 d
BR9	31.81 a	17.19 a	46 b	77 bc	56 bcd	26 bc	21.64 d	20.55 cd	5 a
BR12	18.69 de	7.73 ce	58 de	90 a	65 b	28 bc	20.98 de	17.42 fg	17 cd
Hashikalmi	17.14 ef	11.93 b	30 a	90 a	80 a	11 a	24.56 bc	23.03 a	6 a
Dharail	16.37 e	6.45 de	61 de	69 d	32 e	52 a	23.65 c	21.76 bc	7 a
Morichboti	21.23 cd	9.30 bc	56 cde	83 ab	54 cd	34 bcd	26.33 a	23.21 a	13 b
Dular	24.31 b	12.04 b	51 bed	82 ab	57 bc	30 bc	23.50 c	21.99 ab	14 bc
Kataktara	22.43 bc	11.63 b	48 b	83 ab	65 b	22 ab	21.82 d	19.12 e	12 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level (DMRT). Within a variety, treatment effect was significant at the % level (DMRT).

Correlations between allogamic and agronomic traits in rice

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We studied the correlations between allogamic and agronomic traits in F3-derived lines from the BC2 generation of the cross *Oryza sativa* L. / *Oryza longistaminata* A. Chev. The male parent possesses well-developed floral parts. The F3 lines were evaluated in a completely randomized block design with four replications at two locations in 1986-87.

Allogamic traits evaluated were stigma and anther length, agronomic characters were spikelet and panicle length. Variance and covariance analyses were used.

Table 1 shows the very high coefficients of heritability found for stigma, anther, and spikelet length (0.92, 0.94, and 0.92, respectively). These results indicate that visual selection can be used efficiently for these traits.

Table 1. Coefficient of heritability and average length of stigma, anther, spikelet, and panicle.

Trait	Coefficient of heritability	Average length
Stigma length (mm)	0.9163	1.53 ± 0.27
Anther length (mm)	0.9413	2.62 ± 0.33
Spikelet length (mm)	0.9215	7.39 ± 0.50
Panicle length (cm)	0.6389	19.11 ± 2.81

Table 2. Genetic (G), phenotypic (P), and environmental (E) correlations between stigma, anther, spikelet, and panicle length.

		Anther	Spikelet	Panicle
Stigma	G	0.5548**	0.1565	0.0900
	P	0.5138**	0.1393	0.0349
	E	0.2980	0.1614*	0.2278
Anther	G		-0.0280	0.1979
	P		-0.0076	0.1881
	E		0.2020	0.1231
Spikelet	G			-0.3006
	P			-0.1336
	E			0.3785

Table 2 shows significant and positive genetic and phenotypic correlations between the allogamic characters, indicating that selection for one character can positively change the other.

No significant correlations were found between the two allogamic traits and spikelet and panicle length. □

Screening long-duration rice cultivars for ratooning ability

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We screened 210 entries from IRTP nurseries (1986 International Rice Shallow Water Observational Nurseries [IRSWON], 1986 International Rice Deepwater Observational Nurseries [IRDWON], and 1985 International Upland Rice Yield Nurseries [IURYN]) to select semidwarf long-duration or photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivars that, when sown in November, could be harvested in April/ May with a ratoon crop flowering in late Sep.

Entries were sown 28 Nov 1986 and transplanted 16 Jan 1987 in 2 rows at

20- × 15-cm spacing. Plant height, flowering duration, and yield/ plant were recorded for the main crop. Ability to produce ratoon tillers and flowering behavior of the ratoon were the bases for selecting suitable varieties.

Entries with plants less than 100 cm tall were favored for ratooning, since the main crop was grown under controlled conditions and at higher fertilizer rates (100-22-42 kg NPK/ha) for maximum yield. Nine entries were identified for further study (see table).

RAU4057-35-20, Leuang Yai 148, and C924-9 have semidwarf plant type, high yields, and 1% ratooning ability. Their ratoons flowered the end of Oct,

Ratooning ability of semidwarf photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties. Chinsurah, India, Nov 1986.

Entry	Source	Main crop			Ratooning ability (%)	Ratoon flowering date
		Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (g/plant)		
SPR7292-0-0-0-1	IRSWON	83 ± 4	155	20 ± 7	86	25 Sep 1987
RAU4057-35-20	IRSWON	77 ± 2	136	8 ± 4	100	29 Oct 1987
Leuang Yai 148	IRSWON	77 ± 2	144	20 ± 7	100	29 Oct 1987
IR13149-43-2-P	IRSWON	96 ± 4	153	16 ± 4	100	3 Oct 1987
RTN90-4	IRSWON	96 ± 3	158	11 ± 4	100	26 Oct 1987
TKM9	IRDWON	93 ± 2	123	8 ± 4	100	17 Oct 1987
IR38787-26-2-1-2	IRDWON	100 ± 5	127	9 ± 3	100	18 Oct 1987
NC500	IRDWON	96 ± 7	161	6 ± 4	100	26 Oct 1987
C924-9	IURYN (M)	87 ± 6	140	19 ± 6	100	31 Oct 1987

probably because the lines have shorter critical photoperiod. SPR7292-0-0-0-0-1 planted in late Sep, followed by

IR13 149-43-2-P in early Oct. These dates are more or less desirable for establishing the next crop in Nov. □

Effect of high temperature on rice spikelet fertility

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An abnormally high percentage of Empty spikelets in first crop indica rice occurs in ricefields south of the Yangtze River when flowering takes place in the heat of July. Daily maximum temperatures of 35.5-38.9 °C 1-20 Jul 1988 in Hangzhou lowered rice yields.

We studied the effect of high temperature on spikelet fertility by using different seeding dates to result in

Spikelet fertility at different heading dates.^a Hangzhou, China, 1988.

Variety	Spikelet fertility (%) at heading date		
	27 Jun	1 Jul	5 Jul
Yuanfengzao	93.9 a (15)	84.3 b (15)	76.8 c (15)
Erjiunan 1	89.1 a (11)	80.5 b (15)	34.9 c (10)
Zhe 85-2	88.2 a (15)	87.2 a (15)	76.2 b (15)
Guangluai 4	85.3 a (8)	78.5 b (15)	70.5 c (15)
Zaolian 31	85.2 a (15)	74.3 b (15)	68.5 c (15)
Erjiufeng	79.6 a (7)	78.4 a (15)	58.1 b (15)

^a Figures in parentheses are sample sizes. In a w, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

different heading dates. Spikelet fertility percentage (SFP) was measured on 7-41 randomly selected plants, 3 panicles/plant, for each cultivar and each planting date.

SFP differed significantly among plants with different heading dates from the same cultivar. SFP at normal temperatures 24-28 Jun was higher than at high temperatures 2-14 Jul (see table

Relationship between mean spikelet fertility percentage (Y) of varieties with the same heading date and mean maximum temperature 3 d after heading (X) ($r_{YX} = -0.9570$, $Y = 73.47 - 0.44X$). Cultivars: 1 = Erjiufeng, 2 = Zhefu 802, 3 = Erjiuqing, 4 = Guangluai 4, 5 = Zhong 83-49, 6 = Erjiunan 1, 7 = Yuanfengzao, 8 = Zhe 85-2, 9 = Zaolian 31, 10 = Ainanzao 39, 11 = Guiluai 8, 12 = Zhuxi 26, 13 = Guangliuzao, 14 = Qingganhuang, 15 = Zhuyunnuo, 16 = Ezao 6, 17 = IR58, 18 = IR28, 19 = IR50.